

THE SUBJECT AND OBJECTIVES OF THE SCIENCE OF BIOPHYSICS

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Biophysics as a biomedical science that studies the mechanisms of physical and physico-chemical processes in biological systems. The place of biophysics among the fundamental biological and medical disciplines, the connection with biological and medical sciences. A brief historical sketch of the development of biophysics. Methods and directions of modern biophysics.

The subject of biophysics is the study of the physical and physico-chemical processes underlying life. There are also more comprehensive definitions of biophysics. For example, Nobel Prize winner A. St. Gyorgy claimed that biophysics is "all that is interesting." The term "biophysics" has been entrenched in the scientific literature since 1892, when Carl Pearson, author of the book "The Grammar of Science", stated on its pages: "... science trying to show that the facts of biology – morphology, embryology and physiology form special cases of the application of general physical laws, was called etiology... Perhaps it would be better to call it biophysics." A. Fick and after him other German scientists called this field of knowledge medical physics, but the French physiologist J. A. d'Arsonval, even before K. Pearson's proposal, preferred the term "medical physics" to the phrase "biological physics".

Modern biophysics studies the mechanisms of physical and physico-chemical processes in biological systems at the submolecular, molecular, supramolecular, cellular, tissue, organ and organismic levels.

By the nature of the objects of research, biophysics is a typical biological science. According to the methods of studying biological objects and analyzing research results, biophysics is a kind of branch of physics (according to M.V. Volkenstein, "biophysics is the physics of life phenomena"). She is at the forefront of those areas of biology that transform this oldest area of human knowledge from a humanitarian to an exact science. The introduction of the physical principles of the analysis of biological phenomena into medicine allows it to become not only an art, but also a science. This is the special role of biophysics among other medical theoretical disciplines.

Biophysics is often referred to as a new, young science. So, on November 9, 1934, P.L. Kapitsa wrote: "Biophysics is a completely new field, it came along

with biochemistry to replace the old classical physiology. Instead of studying physiological processes in general... Biophysics and biochemistry study the individual elements of a living being and try to explain its function through the laws of physics and chemistry." Indeed, biophysics has emerged as a separate scientific discipline relatively recently, but the beginnings of biophysics arose immediately after the appearance of works in the field of experimental physics. Thus, some of G. Galileo's research (measuring body temperature, determining the work performed by a person, etc.) can be attributed to biophysical research.

The desire to explain the processes of human and animal life by physical laws was very characteristic of the work of many scientists of the XVII and XVIII centuries (R. Boyle, R. Hooke, I. Newton, P.S. Laplace, A.L. Lavoisier, M.V. Lomonosov and many others). The 19th century was the century of the triumph of analytical methods in the study of biological phenomena. These methods have received the greatest development in physiology, in the depths of which modern biophysics originated. Many physiological processes, including nervous activity, have been tried to explain on the basis of physical laws. Unlike similar attempts by predecessors, such explanations have been largely confirmed experimentally. Hermann Helmholtz measured the rate of propagation of a nerve impulse. Emile Dubois-Raymond studied the bioelectrogenesis of almost all organs and tissues of the body. Ernst Weber explained some properties of hemodynamics based on physical laws. Outstanding discoveries have been made in the field of biophysics of the senses – it is enough to name at least the Weber-Fechner law.

At the same time, the 19th century identified a very characteristic trend in the subsequent development of biophysics. One of the first scientists to notice and confirm this trend was Ivan Mikhailovich Sechenov, the father of Russian physiology. With no less reason, he can be called the founder of Russian biophysics. He used the methods of mathematics and physical chemistry to study respiration, and established quantitative patterns of dissolution of gases in biological fluids. In the works of I.M. Sechenov traces the most promising path of development of physiology and biophysics, primarily related to physical chemistry. In his doctoral dissertation (1860), I.M. Sechenov stated: "A physiologist is a physical chemist dealing with the phenomena of an animal organism."

However, it was only in the 20th century that biophysics became an independent science. Since then, she has begun to study the fundamental problems of biology: heredity and variability, ontogenesis and phylogeny, metabolism and bioenergetics.

Most researchers (biophysicists) of the XVII–XIX centuries considered a living organism as a physical system, and the main method of such a study of biological phenomena was the search for external analogies. It should be noted that even now such a technique is not without success used in biophysics. For example, muscle contraction can be modeled by the reverse piezoelectric effect, amoeboid movement of cells by movements of a mercury drop in an acid solution, conduction of a nerve impulse by migration of a scratch along an iron wire treated with nitric acid (Lilly model), etc.

The cognitive value of such models is rather limited. Often, when modeling the same biological phenomenon, they replace each other following the advent of new technical devices. For example, reflex activity was considered in the time of R. Descartes by analogy with the operation of a steam engine, at the beginning of the last century – a telephone exchange, now – an electronic computer. However, similar (phenomenological) models are needed. They make it possible to clarify some details of phenomena already understood in principle, to create bionic systems that use the laws of biological organization to build complex technical devices, such as robots. Nevertheless, this useful area of physical modeling is not the main one in solving cardinal biophysical problems.

In essence, modern biophysics is the physical chemistry and chemical physics of biological systems. This is the leading direction in the work of two of the world's largest institutes of biophysics of the Russian Academy of Sciences, which are located in the city of Pushchino near Moscow. Many scientific research institutions of the Academy of Sciences, the Academy of Medical Sciences, and the Ministry of Health of Russia are currently dealing with the problems of biophysics. Among them are the Institutes of Physical Chemistry and Chemical Physics of the Russian Academy of Sciences, the Institute of Biophysics of the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation. University departments of biological physics are also engaged in the development of biophysics in our country.

Biophysics is a borderline field of knowledge, and the boundaries between it and a number of other biological sciences are rather arbitrary. When drawing these boundaries, they proceed from the very definition of the subject of biophysics – biophysical studies include studies that reveal the physical, as well as physico-chemical mechanisms of biological processes. In biophysical research, the basic principle of the experimental study of nature is applied – the quantitative analysis of the body's reactions to certain stimuli with the construction of functional dependencies between them. The processes of vital

activity receive a strict interpretation in the form of quantitative patterns, which represent an abstract form of expression of the functional dependence of the reaction on the stimulus.

Physiology has been studying the functions of the body since time immemorial. At different times, the content of physiology has changed. Now she considers function as a form of activity with a certain end result, the manifestation of which is physiological properties (Shidlovsky, 1981). It is impossible to penetrate into their internal mechanisms using traditional physiological approaches to the study of functions. These mechanisms, since they have a physical and chemical nature, are studied by biophysics and biochemistry. The difference between the tasks of biophysics and physiology in the study of body functions can be illustrated by such an example. Investigating biopotentials, a biophysicist is interested, first of all, in the mechanism of occurrence of electromagnetic processes in living tissues, the physico-chemical foundations of this phenomenon, its energy supply, whereas for a physiologist biopotentials are indicators of the vital activity of an organism, serve as a quantitative characteristic of the most important physiological properties (primarily excitability). So, according to the electrocardiogram, the physiologist judges the properties of the heart muscle (automatism, excitability, conduction). He is less concerned with the physico-chemical nature of electrogenesis in the myocardium, this is the main task of the biophysical study of electrical processes in the heart.

Biochemistry, like biophysics, also seeks to penetrate into the mechanisms of physiological phenomena, but studies their chemical nature. The difficulties in distinguishing between biophysical and biochemical research are understandable, but this must be done. "There is no doubt," academician G.M. Frank (1974) argued, "that any manifestations of life and living organisms as a whole are ultimately "chemical machines." However, despite the primacy of chemistry, chemical language and chemical concepts are insufficient to reveal the material essence of the phenomena of life. This primarily applies to the ways of energy conversion, the nature of interaction forces and various physical processes, such as, for example, the generation of electrical potentials, the emergence of mechanical energy, control and regulation mechanisms."

Biophysical methods are created on the basis of physical and physico-chemical methods of studying nature. They must combine properties that are difficult to match: high sensitivity and high accuracy. First of all, the achievements of modern electronics meet this condition. The use of optical

methods is very fruitful. Various spectroscopy methods are widely used, including radio spectroscopy (electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) and nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) methods). Radioisotope techniques have long been in use.

Any study requires that recording devices do not introduce distortions into the process being studied. For a biophysical experiment, compliance with this requirement is especially important. The famous Soviet biophysicist B.N. Tarusov believed that this requirement contains the most important feature of biophysical methods, which distinguishes them from the use of similar methodological techniques in other fields of physics. This somewhat exaggerated formulation of the specifics of biophysical methods has certain grounds. It is difficult to compare any physical system with a living organism due to the unusually high sensitivity of the latter to any effects on it. They do not just disrupt the normal course of biological processes, but cause complex adaptive reactions, diverse in different organs and under different conditions. The distortion of the meaning of true phenomena can be so significant that it becomes impossible to make corrections to artifacts (phenomena that are not peculiar to the studied object in natural conditions and arise during its research), since correction methods used successfully in physics and technology are often fruitless in biophysics.

To better understand the fields of application of biophysical methods, let's consider the main directions of scientific research in biophysics. According to the decision of the International Association of General and Applied Biophysics, these include research at the molecular and cellular levels, as well as the biophysical study of sensory organs and complex systems.

Methods and directions of modern biophysics. Molecular biophysics studies the functional structure and physico-chemical properties of biologically important (biologically functional) molecules, as well as the physical processes that ensure their functioning, examines the thermodynamics of biological systems, energy and charge transfer through biomolecules, and quantum mechanical features of their organization. This part of molecular biophysics is gradually being allocated to a new section called quantum biophysics. In general, the task of molecular biophysics is to reveal the physico-chemical mechanisms of the biological functionality of molecules.

Works on cell biophysics are devoted to the physical and physico-chemical properties of cellular and subcellular structures, the patterns of cell division and differentiation, the peculiarities of their metabolism, as well as the biophysical

mechanisms of specialized cell functions (muscle contraction, secretion, nervous impulses, etc.).

The biophysics of the senses reveals the physical and physico-chemical mechanisms of perception of specific stimuli by the receptor apparatus of sensory systems (analyzers) of humans and animals (at the quantum, molecular, cellular levels).

The task of biophysics of complex systems is to solve common physico-biological problems (origin of life, heredity, variability, etc.) on the basis of physical and mathematical modeling of the most important biological processes. Many biophysicists insist on highlighting another area of biophysical research – the biophysical foundations of ecology. Its content is to clarify the mechanisms of influence on the body of physical and chemical environmental factors. There is a tendency to identify all biophysics with molecular biophysics, which is reflected in M.V. Wolkenstein's textbook "Biophysics", published for students of biological and physical faculties of universities. Such a restriction can be allowed to determine the field of the most relevant scientific research in modern biophysics, although not everyone agrees with this. Thus, academician G.M. Frank argued back in 1974 that "the center of gravity of the physico-chemical consideration of the basis of life phenomena is now shifting to the field of cell biology," since "the phenomena of life arise only in a system called a cell," and, according to E.B. Wilson (1925), "the key to every biological problem must be found in the cell," and modern biophysics began to possess methods that make it possible to make the cell the object of an accurate physical experiment. This does not mean that other areas of biophysical research have a supporting role. According to G.M. Frank, in the development of biophysics, "... the continuity of the line of research from the section that we have designated as "molecular biophysics", further through cell biophysics to the biophysics of complex processes should be observed."

Biophysics is a science that studies the physical and physico-chemical processes that occur in biosystems at different levels of organization and are the basis of physiological acts. The emergence of biophysics occurred as progress in physics, mathematics, chemistry and biology contributed.

Living organisms are an open, self-regulating, self-reproducing and developing heterogeneous system, the most important functional substances in which are biopolymers: proteins and nucleic acids of complex atomic and molecular structure.

Tasks of biophysics:

1. Disclosure of general patterns of behavior of open nonequilibrium systems. Theoretical substantiation of the thermodynamic (t/e) foundations of life.
2. Scientific interpretation of the phenomena of individual and evolutionary development, self-regulation and self-reproduction.
3. Elucidation of the links between the structure and functional properties of biopolymers and other biologically active substances.
4. Creation and theoretical substantiation of physico-chemical methods for the study of biological objects.
5. The physical interpretation of an extensive complex of functional phenomena (generation and distribution of nerve impulses, muscle contraction, reception, photosynthesis, etc.)

Sections of biophysics:

- Molecular – studies the structure and physico-chemical properties, biophysics of molecules. The main objects of research in molecular biophysics are functionally active substances, including proteins and nucleic acids.
- Cell biophysics – studies the features of the structure and functioning of cellular and tissue systems. Cell biophysics deals with supramolecular structures of a living cell, among which membrane structures of cells and subcellular structures occupy a special place.

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